

Analysis of Grey Wolf Optimization GWO in Economic Load Dispatch Problem

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Abstract:

This paper presents GWO flow diagram and algorithm for finding best values which update the generators. GWO algorithm establishes a relation as to how generating level is allocated to each power station analogous to the food divided amongst alpha, beta and delta wolves as per their hierarchy. This idea is tested and then applied to economic dispatch problems. By using IEEE 14 and IEEE 30 Bus system taking into account line impedances, half line charging susceptance, MVA rating the fuel cost coefficient and emission coefficient are calculated. generator power, Voltage at each bus, and transmission losses are also incorporated to find the Generated cost.

Keywords — Economic Load Dispatch, Grey wolf optimization GWO, Power Systems, Optimization Techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Economic Load Dispatch (ELD) can be defined as the process of allocating generation level to the generating units, so that the system load is supplied entirely and most economically. For an interconnected system, it is necessary to minimize the expenses. The economic load dispatch is used to define the production level of each plant, so that the total cost of generation and transmission is minimum for a prescribed schedule of load. The objective of economic load dispatch is to minimize the overall cost of generation.

There are many conventional methods that are used to solve economic load dispatch problem such as Lagrange multiplier methods, lambda iteration method and Newton- Raphson method. In the conventional methods, it is difficult to solve the optimal economic problem if the load changed.

It needs to compute the economic load dispatch each time which uses a long time in each of computation loops. So the idea of balanced economic and emission dispatch makes it a multi objective optimization problem to be solved.

For solving this problem, a Grey wolf optimization GWO optimization is chosen, and 14bus and 30bus IEEE test systems are taken and simulated results are obtained.

Fig.1 Flow chart of GWO

III. GREY WOLF OPTIMIZATION APPLIED TO ELD

The implementation of GWO algorithm to solve ELD complex problem is described as follows:

1. For the chosen test system, read the input data to compute the total fuel cost of the system.
2. Initialization of GWO parameters i.e., population size N and select the stopping criteria.
3. Select the number of design variables, D and initialize the design variables i.e., the real power outputs for each generating units in the chosen system.
4. In accordance to the population size, the design variable is generated randomly within the limits using where $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, D$ Therefore, the matrix of $Du \times N$ is initialized using
5. The fitness of each population is calculated using FT. After sorting the fitness value in descending order as beta E and third minimal as delta G grey wolves.
6. The individual population corresponding to F TD,
7. Determine A_i and B_i , $i = 1, 2$ and 3
8. Update the position of each grey wolf Eqns.
9. Select the termination criterion 4 to 7 will be repeated till the termination criteria is reached by the algorithm.

A. Fuel Cost Coefficient

Bus number	a_i	b_i	c_i	P_{min}	P_{max}
1	100	200	10	50	200
2	120	150	10	20	80
5	40	180	20	15	50
8	60	100	10	10	35
11	40	180	20	10	30
13	100	150	10	12	40

B. Emission Coefficient

Bus number	α_i	β_i	γ_i	ξ_i	λ_i
1	4.091	-5.554	6.490	$2 * 10^{-4}$	2.857
2	2.543	-6.047	5.638	$5 * 10^{-4}$	3.333
5	4.258	-5.094	4.586	$1 * 10^{-6}$	8.00
8	5.426	-3.556	3.380	$2 * 10^{-3}$	2.00
11	4.258	-5.094	4.586	$1 * 10^{-6}$	8.000
13	6.131	-5.555	5.151	$1 * 10^{-5}$	6.667

C. IEEE 14 BUS DATA

Line number	From bus	To bus	Line impedance (p.u.)		Half line charging susceptance (p.u.)	MVA rating
			Resistance	Reactance		
1	1	2	0.01938	0.05917	0.02640	120
2	1	5	0.05403	0.22304	0.02190	65
3	2	3	0.04699	0.19797	0.01870	36
4	2	4	0.05811	0.17632	0.02460	65
5	2	5	0.05695	0.17388	0.01700	50
6	3	4	0.06701	0.17103	0.01730	65
7	4	5	0.01335	0.04211	0.00640	45
8	4	7	0	0.20912	0	55
9	4	9	0	0.55618	0	32
10	5	6	0	0.25202	0	45
11	6	11	0.09498	0.1989	0	18
12	6	12	0.12291	0.25581	0	32
13	6	13	0.06615	0.13027	0	32
14	7	8	0	0.17615	0	32
15	7	9	0	0.11001	0	32
16	9	10	0.03181	0.0845	0	32
17	9	14	0.12711	0.27038	0	32
18	10	11	0.08205	0.19207	0	12
19	12	13	0.22092	0.19988	0	12
20	13	14	0.17093	0.34802	0	12

D. GWO for 14 bus system

TABLE I
GWO for 14 bus system

S.No.	ALGORITHM	GWO 14 BUS SYSTEM
1	Fuel Cost (rs/hr.)	690.45
2	Emission (kg/hr)	270.5423
	Generator Power	
3	G1	175.1
4	G2	35
5	G3	20.6
6	G4	16.25
7	G5	11.79
	VOLTAGE AT BUS	14 BUS SYSTEM
8	b1	1.06
9	b2	1.041
10	b3	1.023
11	b4	1.012
12	b5	1.01
13	b6	1.071
14	b7	1.021
15	b8	1.01
16	b9	1.048
17	b10	1.065
18	b11	1.082
19	b12	1.061
20	b13	1.071
21	b14	1.0516
22	Generator Cost	700

Fig.2 GWO Generator power

E. IEEE 14 BUS system Graphs for PSO and GWO

Fig.3 GWO Voltage at each bus

Fig.1 GWO fuel cost and emission

Fig.4 GWO Transmission loss

Fig.5 GWO Generator cost

F. GWO for 30bus system

TABLE III
GWO FOR 30 BUS SYSTEM

S.NO.	ALGORITHM	GWO 30 BUS SYSTEM
1	Fuel Cost (rs/hr.)	756.0183
2	Emission (kg/hr)	343.0071
	Generator Power	
3	G1	200
4	G2	20.029
5	G3	15.032
6	G4	10.42
7	G5	10.03
8	G6	12
	VOLTAGE AT BUS	30 BUS SYSTEM
9	b1	1.06
10	b2	1.04
11	b3	1.024
12	b4	1.0163
13	b5	1.1
14	b6	1.0143
15	b7	1.004
16	b8	1.01
17	b9	1.0523
18	b10	1.043
19	b11	1.082
20	b12	1.0599
21	b13	1.071
22	b14	1.044
23	b15	1.03
24	b16	1.046
25	b17	1.040

26	b18	1.02
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S.NO.	ALGORITHM	GWO 30 BUS SYSTEM
27	b19	1.02
28	b20	1.0311
29	b21	1.033
30	b22	1.034
31	b23	1.0294
32	b24	1.023
33	b25	1.01
34	b26	1.0022
35	b27	1.026
36	b28	1.012
37	b29	1.0065
38	b30	0.9951
39	Transmission Loss	12.83
40	Generator Cost	810

G. IEEE 30 BUS system Graphs for PSO and GWO

Fig.6 IEEE30-GWO Fuel cost and Emission

Fig.7 IEEE30-PSO Generator Power

	1	2	3	4
1	1.0600	1.0430	1.0246	

VOLTAGE AT EACH BUS(pu)

Fig.8 IEEE30-GWO Voltage at Each Bus

	1
1	12.8381

Transmission Loss

Fig.9 IEEE30-GWO Transmission loss

Fig.10 IEEE30-PSO Generator cost

CONCLUSIONS

This work adopts the best meta-heuristic optimization techniques to solve the problem of balance between economy and emissions. By analyzing both the cases IEEE 14 and IEEE 30 Bus system it is observed that the generator cost and emission value is better than obtained by conventional methods for calculating other load dispatch. Therefore, the solution for high -end systems can be obtained in a shorter time compared to conventional methods. The reliability of the proposed algorithm is very good when the program is run in a different way, which shows that no matter how the program processes, it can get the same answer to the problem.

REFERENCES

1. Bo Li and Jingwen Wang, "Economic Dispatch Methods for Smart Grid" School of Automation Engineering, Northeast Electric Power University, Jilin, China 07 December 2021
2. Widi Arbovo, " Comparison Study on economic load dispatch using meta heuristic algorithm" Gazi university journal of science· March 2022
3. Jun Du, Zongnan Zhang, Menghan Li and Kongge Zhu, "Optimal scheduling of integrated energy system based on improved grey wolf optimization algorithm" School of Energy and Power, Jiangsu University 02 May 2022
4. Farshad resaei, hamid reza safavi, and Mohammed azmi "An Enhanced Grey Wolf Optimizer with a Velocity-Aided Global Search Mechanism " 22 Jan 2022
5. Abdullah Alzaqebah, Ibarahim Aljarah and Omar AL qaidi "A Modified Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm for an Intrusion Detection System" Department of Applied Informatics, Vytautas Magnus University, 44404 Kaunas, Lithuania Feb 2022
6. Sobia Pervaiz, Zia Ul-Qayyum, Waqas Haider Bangyal, Liang Gao, and Jamil Ahmad , "A Systematic Literature Review on Particle Swarm Optimization Techniques for

- Medical Diseases Detection” I Department of Computer Science, Abasyn University Islamabad Campus 2021
7. Tijani muhammed , Adepoju Gafari , Ayoade Morufu a., Afolalu Oladele f., Oladiran Taoeek a. “Economic load dispatch of Nigerian power system considering valve point loading effect through interior point method” *Electrical & Electronic Engineering Department, Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Nigeria* April 22
 8. Manish Parihar, M.K. Bhaskar "Review of Power System Blackout" *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science -IJRIAS* vol.3 issue 6 June 2018, pp.08-13 URL: <https://www.rsisinternational.org/journals/ijrias/DigitalLibrary/Vol.3&Issue6/08-13.pdf>.
 9. Emmanuel Gbenga DADA and Shafi'i Muhammad ABDULHAMID “Application of Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm: Recent Trends, Issues, and Possible Horizons” *GU J Sci* 35(2): 485-504 (2022) 11 May 2021
 10. Seyedali Mirjalili, Seyed Mohammad Mirjalili and Andrew Lewis, “Grey wolf optimizer” *Department of Electrical Engineering, Shahid Beheshti University, G.C. 1983963113, Tehran, Iran* 2013 Elsevier
 11. Moumita Pradha, Provas Kumar Roy and Tandra Pal “Grey wolf optimization applied to economic load dispatch problems” *Department of Electrical Engineering, Jalpaiguri Government Engineering College, Jalpaiguri, West Bengal, India* 22 April 2016
 12. Nitish Chopra I, Gourav Kumar and Shivani Mehta “Hybrid GWO-PSO Algorithm for Solving Convex Economic Load Dispatch Problem” *International Journal of Research in Advent Technology, Vol.4, No.6, June 2016*
 13. M.R. AlRashidi, and M.E. El-Hawary, “Survey of Particle Swarm Optimization Applications in Electric Power Systems,” *IEEE transaction on evolutionary computation*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp.913- 917, august 2009.
 14. D. W. Ross and S. Kim, “Dynamic economic dispatch of generation,” *IEEE Transaction on power Apparatus and Systems*, vol.1, no. 6, pp.22- 28, 1980.
 15. K.T. Chaturvedi, M. Pandit, and L. Srivastava, “Self-organizing hierarchical particle Swarm optimization for non-convex economic dispatch,” *IEEE Transaction on power systems*, pp.1079- 1087, 2008.
 16. R. Rajabioum, “Cuckoo optimization algorithm,” *Applied Soft Computing*, pp.5508-5518, November 2011.
 17. K.T. Chaturvedi, M. Pandit, and L. Srivastava, “Particle swarm optimization with time varying acceleration coefficients for non-convex economic power dispatch”, *International Journal of Electrical and Power Energy System*. pp.249–257, June 2009.
 18. B.R. Adarsh, T. Raghunathan, T. Jayabarathi, X.S. Yang, “Economic dispatch using chaotic bat algorithm” *Energy*, pp. 666- 675, 2016.
 19. G. Kumar, R. Singh, “Economic dispatch of power system optimization with power generation schedule using evolutionary technique,” *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering*, vol. 3, Issue 7, pp.10715-10722, July 2014.
 20. D.C. Walters, and G.B. Sheble, “Genetic algorithm solution of economic dispatch with valve point loading,” *IEEE Transaction on power systems*, pp.1325-1332, 199359.
 21. Manish Parihar, M.K. Bhaskar, Dharmendra Jain, Digvijay Sarvate, Deepak Bohra. "Voltage Stability Analysis of Power System using Power World Simulator", Volume 5, Issue XI, *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)* Page No: 2508-2515, ISSN : 2321-9653, <http://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2018.11371>.
 22. El-Gallad, M. El-Hawary, A. A. Sallam, and A. Kalas, “Swarm intelligence for hybrid cost dispatch problem,” in *Proceeding of the Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 2, pp. 753–757, 2001.
 23. X.S. Yang, S.S.S. Hosseini, and A.H. Gandomi, “Firefly algorithm for solving nonconvex economic dispatch problems with valve loading effect,” *Applied Soft Computing* 2012, pp.1180- 1186.
 24. M.H. Sulaiman, Z.N. Zakaria, M.I. Mohd-Rashid, and S.R.A. Rahim, “A new swarm intelligence technique for solving economic dispatch problem,” in *Power Engineering and Optimization IEEE Conference*, pp. 199-202, 2013.
 25. J. Sun, V. Palade, X.J. Wu, W. Fang, and Z. Wang, “Solving the power economic dispatch problem with generator constraints by random drift particle swarm optimization,” *IEEE Transaction on industrial Informatics*, pp.222-232, 2014.
 26. T.A.A. Victoire, and A.E. Jeyakumar, “Hybrid PSO-SQP for economic dispatch with Valve- point effect,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, pp.51-59, 2004.60
 27. D. Swagatam, and P.N. Suganthan, “Problem definition and evaluation criteria for CEC 2011 competition on testing evolutionary algorithms on real world optimization problems,” *Technical report*, Dec 2010.